

Seed technology

Influence of alkalinity on rice germination and growth

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We studied germination and seedling growth of six rice varieties at different pH levels. Tap water was used as the medium, with a pH of 7.0 and an EC of 1.0. Potassium hydroxide and acetic acid were used to adjust solution pH to 6.5, 7.5, 8.5, 9.5, and 10.5.

We placed 10 seeds of a variety in a petri dish, replicating each variety three times. Water volume was kept constant in each dish by adding solution. Germinated seeds were counted after 6 d. Seedling height and root length were measured at 6 and 10 d after transplanting (DT) (see table).

Overall germination ranged from 86 to 100% at all pH levels. Maximum germination for all varieties occurred at pH 8.5-9.5. HKR120 had the tallest seedlings at 6 DT. Seedling height,

Effect of alkalinity on growth of rice seedlings.

Variety	pH at 6 DT ^a						pH at 10 DT					
	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	Mean	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	Mean
	<i>Seedling height (cm)</i>											
Jaya	2.9	2.5	2.6	2.7	1.8	2.5	4.4	4.6	4.2	3.2	2.3	3.8
PR103	3.7	3.9	3.2	2.4	1.7	3.0	4.1	4.5	5.9	3.1	2.1	3.9
HKR120	3.2	4.8	3.9	3.3	1.8	3.4	4.2	4.7	5.4	3.3	1.9	3.9
PR106	3.1	3.3	2.9	2.6	2.8	2.9	4.2	4.4	4.5	3.2	3.6	3.9
PR109	2.4	3.1	2.6	2.4	1.7	2.4	3.4	4.3	4.4	2.9	2.5	3.5
Pal 579	3.3	3.0	3.1	3.6	2.0	3.0	3.9	4.2	4.6	4.0	2.5	3.9
Mean	3.1	3.4	3.1	2.8	1.2		4.0	4.5	4.8	3.3	2.5	
LSD (0.05)	V = 0.03, pH = 0.02, V × pH = 0.15						V = ns, pH = 0.13, V × pH = ns					
	<i>Root length (cm)</i>											
Jaya	2.6	2.6	2.4	3.1	1.8	2.5	3.5	3.6	3.2	2.6	1.6	2.2
PR103	4.9	6.1	4.7	2.1	1.4	3.8	5.2	6.6	5.6	1.9	1.4	3.1
HKR120	2.4	4.0	2.9	2.7	1.5	2.7	2.9	4.5	4.5	2.1	1.3	3.0
PR106	3.4	4.7	4.0	3.7	3.8	3.9	3.6	3.8	4.0	3.1	3.3	3.6
PR109	3.7	4.0	3.1	2.9	2.1	3.2	3.2	3.6	3.8	3.8	1.7	3.0
Pal 579	3.8	3.0	5.3	4.8	2.0	4.0	3.4	3.5	4.1	3.9	1.8	3.3
Mean	3.5	4.2	3.7	3.2	2.1		3.6	4.3	4.2	2.7	1.8	
LSD (0.05)	V = 0.01, pH = 0.10, V × pH = 0.65						V = 0.11, pH = 0.09, V × pH = 0.57					

^aDT = days after transplanting. ^bns = not significant.

however, was not significantly different among varieties at 10 DT. Seedlings were tallest at pH 7.5 at 6 DT and at pH 8.5 at

10 DT. Pal 579 had the longest roots at 6 DT and PR106 at 10 DT; Jaya had the shortest. Roots were longest at pH 7.5. ■

Crop and resource management

Soils

Effect of green manures on ammonia-release pattern in rice soils

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We conducted an incubation study on a submerged clay loam (Vertic Ustropepts) and sandy loam (Typic Haplustalf) with green manure (GM) incorporation. Ipomoea (*Ipomoea cornea*), water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*), gliricidia (*Gliricidia sepium*), dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), and calotrophis (*Calotrophis gigantea*) were incorporated at 12.5 t/ha fresh weight. Water level was maintained

Ammoniacal N (ppm)

at 5 ± 1 cm to keep soil submerged. We monitored ammonia-release pattern from the soils at 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 30, and 45 d after incorporation (DAI).

In the clay loam, peak NH_4^+ -N concentration was observed after 30 DAI for ipomoea and water hyacinth; the highest concentration was at 20 DAI for the other GMs. In the sandy loam, NH_4^+ -N concentration for all GMs increased progressively up to 20 DAI, after which it declined (see figure). This difference between soils could be related to their pattern degradation and minerali

N mineralization of green manures. (a) Ipomoea/water hyacinth. (b) Neem/gliceridial/calotrophis.

zation processes. The delay in ammonia release from the GM in the clay loam might be due to the soil's high buffering capacity and its behavior in supporting microflora under submergence, which are involved in mineralization and immobilization turnover.

S. aculeata, followed by ipomoea, had the highest NH_4^+ -N concentration of the

treatments in both soils up to 20 DAI. Variation in the ammonia released could be attributed to the type of GM added and to the degradation and subsequent N mineralization from these materials. Unconventional GMs, such as ipomoea and water hyacinth, degraded more slowly than popular leguminous GMs *S. aculeata* and *gliricidia*.

Soil traits, particularly texture and its associated characteristics, influence decomposition of added organic material. Similarly, chemical composition of organic matter, such as lignin and total carbon, controls mineralization and release of plant nutrients. ■

Effect of urea application timing on ammonia volatilization in green manure-amended wetland rice soil

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Laboratory and greenhouse studies on mineralization of green manure (GM) show that peak NH_4^+ -N release occurs about 10 d after incorporation. We studied the effects of urea application timing on floodwater parameters and ammonia volatilization in a wetland ricefield during 1990.

The soil is a calcareous, alluvial sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH of 8.4, 0.35% organic C, 0.06% total N, CEC of 5.3 c mol/kg, and percolation rate of 12 cm/d. Treatments included 60 kg N/ha as GM *Sesbania aculeata*; GM and various combinations of 60 kg N/ha as urea applied at transplanting, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and 42 DT; and 120 and 180 kg N/ha as urea applied in three splits (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Floodwater samples collected between 1200 and 1400 h were analyzed for pH, ammoniacal N, and temperature to calculate the vapor pressure

Effect of green manure and urea N on vapor pressure of ammonia (pNH_3) in floodwater.

•Values in parentheses show kg N/ha applied at transplanting, 21 DT, and/or 42 DT. •GM supplied 60 kg N/ha.

of ammonia (pNH_3). Ammonia volatilization was estimated directly by capturing the ammonia flush from the soil in two acid traps per plot.

The pNH_3 in floodwater peaked two days after fertilizer application, followed by a sharp decline on the third day. It remained low until urea was topdressed at 21 or 42 DT (see figure), at which time pNH_3 again increased rapidly. The pNH_3 values were higher in the GM plus urea treatments than in the urea treatments at transplanting and at topdressing, suggesting a higher potential of ammonia loss in GM-amended soil. Ammoniacal N concentration and floodwater alkalinity supported the observation (data not reported).

The higher alkalinity ($CO_3^{2-} + HCO_3^-$) in GM-amended treatments was attributed to an increase in partial pressure of CO_2 during GM decomposition. The sharp decline of pNH_3 was commensurate with a decline of ammoniacal N concentration in floodwater, probably due to volatilization losses and downward movement by mass flow. Although pNH_3 did not provide an absolute measure of ammonia loss, results suggest that percolating soils generally have lower potential for ammonia volatilization.

As expected, the direct estimate showed a low amount of ammonia volatilization, ranging from 2.9 to 9.0 kg N/ha (see table). The losses were selectively higher during the 7 d following fertilizer application in the GM plus urea treatment at transplanting compared with GM treatments and urea application at 21 or 42 DT; the GM plus no urea treatment showed lower volatile ammonia loss.

GM-amended wetland rice soils undergo lower volatilization losses when urea is applied at active tillering or panicle initiation rather than at transplanting. Ammonia volatilization, however, is not an important loss mechanism in soil with a high percolation rate. ■

Effect of urea and GM N on ammonia volatilization loss (kg N/ha) at different days after transplanting. PAU, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Days after transplanting									Total
	0-4	4-7	7-10	10-21	21-25	25-30	30-42	42-47	47-52	
N (40-40-40) ^a	1.0	0.3	0.2	0.3	1.7	0.7	0.5	0.9	0.6	6.2
N (60-60-60)	1.7	0.9	0.4	0.4	1.9	0.8	0.5	1.8	0.8	9.0
GM ^b +N (0-0-0)	1.0	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	2.9
GM+N (60-0-0)	2.8	1.8	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	6.6
GM+N (0-60-0)	1.0	0.6	0.3	0.2	2.3	0.8	0.4	0.3	0.2	6.6
GM+N (0-0-60)	1.0	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	2.0	1.0	5.7
GM+N (20-20-20)	1.3	0.7	0.3	0.2	1.1	0.4	0.3	1.0	0.4	5.7

^aValues in parentheses show kg N/ha applied at transplanting, 21 DT, and/or 42 DT. ^bGM supplied 60 kg N/ha.